

The Impact of Transgender Representation: A Comparative Study of Select Movies

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Introduction

2013 saw the media take centre stage as a means of instruction. In addition to movies and television shows, other media that continuously assault our senses include books, newspapers, magazines, and the Internet. However, consumers don't always leave educational media with fresh knowledge in their minds. Many media portray fictional people in real-world contexts, and viewers sometimes take it for granted that authors, producers, and performers don't always properly and accurately depict real-world scenarios. When consumers base their expectations on what they read in books or watch on television, they could unintentionally assume things about settings or cultures that are just not true. If false presumptions are perpetuated repeatedly, they turn into prejudices and can result in discrimination. These preconceptions perpetuate themselves by repeated reproduction and portrayals, creating a vicious cycle. In this way, whether or not these representations and opinions are accurate, the media both informs and reflects the views of our society. Since the media has such a strong influence on our opinions and is so ingrained in our lives, educated viewers need to ensure that the stories and material they are exposed to are morally sound and do not have the potential to promote discrimination or prejudice.

For a considerable amount of time, researchers in psychology and communications have maintained that there is a connection between young people's development and their socialisation to Media, especially television. Media socialisation is an essential factor influencing how people pick up static or stereotypical identities and other representations. The process is defined as exposure to mass media messages—such as those found in newspapers, radio, television, and the Internet—instructing people in socially acceptable behaviour. These media sources indirectly mediate or facilitate learning and directly impact behavioural functioning and cognitive ability (Adams & Stevenson, 2012). According to George Gerbner's cultivation theory (Gerbner, 1998), viewers repeatedly exposed to TV images eventually come to believe that the images they see are accurate representations of real-world situations. This theory helps verify correlations between the amount of TV exposure and real-life perceptions. When the cultivation theory is applied to transgender people's TV-watching habits, especially in young people, it suggests that transgender characters shown in television and media images will be accepted as legitimate role models of expected and acceptable transgender behaviour. As a result, how people are portrayed in the media greatly influences how society views people and how they define themselves. This paper attempts to examine how media portrayals of transgender people affect their mental health and sense of self, with a focus on both domestic (Bollywood) and international viewpoints.

The way transgender people are portrayed in the media can have a significant impact on them because of how frequently they experience severe social stigma and are subjected to marginalisation. Seeing characters that appear, feel, and behave like them can be a massive boost to a marginalised person's journey, especially in a world that is often harsh to those who are marginalised by race, ethnicity, class, sexual orientation, gender, and political position. It is impossible to overestimate the influence of mainstream or alternative media

representation. The absence and deception of representation can have severe adverse emotional effects, particularly for marginalised people. Conversely, there are a plethora of advantages of complex and autonomous forms of representation. Research looking into the *Social Surrogacy Hypothesis* shows that thinking about beloved TV characters seems to produce a sense of belongingness. Jaye L. Derrick, Shira Gabriel, and Kurt Hugenberg's research at the University of Buffalo and Miami University served as the basis for the development of the *Social Surrogacy Hypothesis* (2008). It claims that people's reactions to their favourite television shows are frequently similar to their reactions to social interactions. This is frequently mentioned as a benefit of TV viewing. We are social creatures with a great need to fit in, feel liked by others, and be a part of their lives. Binge-watching a television show or a movie can help someone who may be feeling lonely by satisfying part of their social requirements due to the effect of social surrogacy. It is possible for someone who is feeling alone to tune in to a show and get a sense of belongingness. Naturally, this can also be harmful if it makes people avoid social connections in real life, but it can also be an excellent source of support for those going through difficult or transitional times.

Furthermore, a lot of cisgender people might not have ever encountered a transgender person. It's possible that these individuals are unaware of what it means to be transgender. Even though sexual orientation and gender identity are unrelated, a lot of people mistake being transgender for homosexuality. These individuals are the ones who, as a result of media representations of the transgender community, grow to mistrust and prejudice the community. Even transgender persons terrify a great deal of people. Perhaps if transgender characters were portrayed truthfully, this fear might not exist. Therefore, this creates a need for more accurate and authentic representations.

Transgender people have historically been either invisible or inaccurately portrayed in the media. Early portrayals of transgender characters frequently reinforced stereotypes by casting them as tragic, comedic, or villainous characters. The way transgender people have been portrayed has led to discrimination and misunderstanding in society, which has also led to a negative effect on their mental health. Movies featuring transgender characters consistently portray them as strange and disturbed, thereby making them dangerous and alienated. An outstanding illustration of how the heteronormative gender and sexual order are maintained and reinforced while the transgender figure is othered is found in the movie *The Silence of the Lambs* (1991). The self-castrated killer in this movie skins and kills young women in order to sew them into a body suit. The murderer's motivation is described as coming from a desire to own and transform into the unachievable—a biological woman. His "illusion" that he was born into the wrong body and is thus essentially cheated out of what is rightfully his is the source of his rage. The trans danger in movies like *The Silence of the Lambs* is usually neutralised by the killing of the trans character by a figurehead who stands for stability and order. In this movie, the biological or "natural" female prevails over the unnatural, delegitimised pretender. The movie makes the following inferences: that one's biological sex is predetermined from birth, that the urge to alter one's biological sex stems from abnormality and insanity, and that the ultimate, unachievable goal of altering one's sex results in both lunacy and murder.

The 1999 movie *Boys Don't Cry* is based on the true tale of Brandon Teena, a teenage transgender Nebraskan. After running away from home and being expelled from his friend's house, he meets a group of friends who take him in. He establishes a bond with one of them. It isn't until they discover a court summons with his female name, Teena Brandon, printed on it that they discover he is transgender. His girlfriend is then forced to gaze at his genitalia by two of his friends who attack him. Later on, they beat and raped him. Before Brandon leaves town, he hides away at the home of another buddy, but his attackers find out where he is and shoot him (Pierce, 1999). The film was enormously popular. The film's presence at the Oscars is evidence of the impact it made on the viewers. A transgender character who wasn't a violent or unstable criminal or a sexual offender starred in a movie for the first time (Rigney, 2003). Although Brandon Teena was a real person who was attacked and killed in Falls City, Nebraska, in 1993, the film's director, Kimberly Pierce, acknowledges that she used artistic license with her story (historyvshollywood.com, 2013). For the first time, a transgender character was viewed as the story's hero, and the movie raised awareness of the transgender community and the violence transgender people frequently experience. The terrible murder and violent rape in the movie had a profound impact on viewers. Hilary Swank, the actress who played Brandon in the movie, recognised Brandon and his unique, tragic story in her winning speech (historyvshollywood.com, 2013). Even though Brandon Teena became a hero for viewers who identify as cisgender, he turned into a cautionary tale for transgender viewers about the consequences of coming out publicly (Rigney, 2003). According to Vito Russo, "Mainstream films about homosexuality are not for gays. They address themselves exclusively to the majority. How should 'we' (society) react to 'them' (me)?" (Russo, 1987, p. 325). Russo's question is echoed

in *Boys Don't Cry*, which also addresses the general public. Queer viewers are advised to exercise greater caution while pushing the boundaries of gender and/or sexuality because doing so may result in violence, inept or inaction on the part of the authorities, and sensationalism in the media.

For transgender individuals who have concealed their identities from everyone but themselves, *Boys Don't Cry* also contains a less-than-encouraging message of what happens to transgender people who have the bravery to stand up for what is right for them. The movie, however, did increase awareness of transgender issues in the US. The existence of transgender people and the persecution they face for being who they are was brought to the attention of cisgender audiences. The fact that a film such as this is regarded as so revolutionary shows how little attention Hollywood usually pays to underrepresented communities. It is interesting to note that the antagonists in the movie are also members of a non-marginalized group. Usually, it is the cisgender people who are the heroes of the movie, but in the case of *Boys Don't Cry*, the roles are reversed.

Unlike most other parts of the world, India has a rich history and culture surrounding transgender individuals. Hijras are a group of third-gender individuals who have been present in the Indian subcontinent for a very long period. They are mentioned in Indian scriptures dating back 3000 years, and they have played a significant role in India's mythology, culture, and religious environment ever since. One may imagine that transgender persons in India would be widely represented in the media in a way that is appropriate, nuanced, and reflective of the rich history of transgender people in India. Regrettably, this is not the case, particularly within the mainstream. The majority of the already scant depictions of transgender individuals in Indian Cinema are typified by objectification, dehumanisation, simplicity, and derision.

When it comes to mainstream Hindi transgender cinema, *Tamanna*, *Dayarra*, *Darmiyaan*, and *Laxmii* are just a few examples of films that feature trans depictions. *Laxmii* is a 2020 movie by director Raghava Lawrence, and Akshay Kumar plays the titular character. Due to a complicated series of events, Asif, played by Akshay Kumar, ends up consuming some blood from the buried corpse of a transgender woman, Laxmi. Asif is then possessed by the ghost of Laxmi, who causes him to act effeminately during the day and go on murderous rampages during the night. His family then hires an exorcist, who confines the ghost and makes it recount its tale. Laxmi recounts that she was cast out of her parent's home for being gender non-conforming, and a generous Muslim man took her in. She puts forth a lot of effort and eventually purchases land to build a hospital for underprivileged individuals. But Girja, a corrupt MLA, takes illegal possession of the land and murders Laxmi and her adopted family. He then goes on to bury the corpses in the same land. After learning the backstory of Laxmi, Asif feels terrible for her and allows her to use his body to exact her revenge on Girja. The movie has a happy ending because Laxmi finally gets her revenge, and Asif builds a hospital in the same land. It is revealed in the end that Laxmi continues to reside in Asif's body and emerges when needed.

In the movie's opening scene, Asif says, “*Jis din maine bhoot dekh liya na, churiya pehen lunga*” (the day I witness a ghost, I will wear bangles). There are several issues with this statement. The phrasing strongly suggests that he would never, under normal circumstances, take on a feminine attribute, suggesting that men wearing bangles is an intrinsically abnormal act. The claim is blatantly transmisogynistic, an intersectional kind of sexism that stems from heterosexual men's anxiety over being perceived as feminine. Secondly, conflating transitioning to a boastful challenge is detrimental. Asif only transitions because he has been possessed by a ghost. This, too, is a transphobic myth that compares the idea of transitioning – which is a kind and educational process for all trans people – to demonic possession. Additionally, the scene that introduces Asif's “trans” features is quite stereotyped and reductive. Using Dutch angles, the other characters' reactions, and the background score, Asif is presented as fundamentally malevolent and diabolical while trying on sarees and bracelets. He uses terms like “*halkat*” and “*kya re*”, further demonstrating his rudeness and incivility. Transgender people are presented as a menace to the society. The first night after his transition, Asif begins going on killing sprees, playing into the transphobic stereotype of the cross-dressing killer, which paints transgender individuals as deranged, immoral, criminal, mentally sick, and undeserving of compassion.

All three movies mentioned have one more thing in common besides dealing with transgender characters is that cisgender actors play the said transgender characters: Ted Levine in *The Silence of the Lambs*, Hilary Swank in *Boys Don't Cry*, and Akshay Kumar in *Laxmii*. This is problematic for many reasons. It conveys the idea that transgender women are just men dressed in sarees and gowns. Additionally, giving transgender people the opportunity to tell their own stories gives them control over their narrative. Furthermore, they can draw on their own past experiences to fit the role, something that is not always the case for cisgender actors who typically play similar roles. In terms of writing, the movie industry, in particular, has to acknowledge that transgender characters can exist in stories even when they don't address gender

identification. Because the focus is only on the gender identity of these characters, the characters seem to be one note and forced into the story.

Being transgender is just one part of who someone is, and they can exist without their transness being the main focus of the story. It can just be one facet of their character. As Casey Plett once said, “Trans people don’t need more visibility. We need better visibility – in all its mess”. This connects to the idea of the cisgender gaze, according to which a lot of transgender media is produced to appeal to a cisgender audience. They wish to view transgender people as either strange or eccentric or as helpless victims who can be sympathised with and who need rescuing. Effective transgender representation can also be attained by treating trans persons with the same respect and decency as any other rich and nuanced story, whether or not that narrative involves interaction or acceptance of the transgender identity. Caricaturistic depictions of transgender people arise when writers create transgender characters without being sensitive to and conscious of transphobic prejudice.

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